

Trapping the tetrahedral intermediate in the 1,3-shift of an acetyl group using a triisopropylsilyl group

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Attempted silylation of (2*RS*,3*RS*,4*RS*)-3-hydroxy-2,4-dimethylhexyl acetate **3** gave neither the primary nor the secondary silyl ether, but the stereoisomeric silyl ethers **9** and **10** of the tetrahedral intermediate in the 1,3-transfer of the acetyl group.

In the course of synthetic work designed to achieve a total synthesis of ebelactone-a in which all the stereochemistry would be controlled by methods based on organosilicon chemistry¹, we needed to convert the alcohol **1**² into the triisopropylsilyl-protected β -hydroxyaldehyde **2**. This gave us what looked like a fairly simple problem of protecting group manipulation. The attachment of the triisopropylsilyl protecting group to the secondary hydroxyl required that the primary hydroxyl be already protected, and an acetyl group was our first choice. The conversion of the silyl group to a hydroxyl³ to give the monoacetate **3** was the key step. It did not seem to present any problems, but there was potentially a pitfall in the subsequent silylation of the secondary hydroxyl to give the intermediate **5**. In this step, the acetyl group might easily migrate from the primary hydroxyl to the secondary **3** \rightarrow **4**, and we would find the silyl group on the wrong oxygen atom in the derivative **6**. This is not an unreasonable fear, since acyl groups can easily undergo shifts from one hydroxyl to another in 1,3-diols⁴. Although it would almost certainly be thermodynamically uphill, such a 1,3-shift would release the intermediate **4** with a primary hydroxyl group, which can be expected to react with the silylating agent much faster than the secondary hydroxyl group would in the intermediate **3**. It might even be tiresome to prove just where each of the two groups was – only after we had hydrolysed the acetate and oxidised the alcohol, would the difference between an aldehyde and a ketone make it unambiguous which of the two possible products **5** or **6** we had. In the event, we obtained a third isomer, as well as finding our way to a solution to the whole problem.

Results and Discussion

The work described in this paper was carried out with racemic compounds. Our first attempt at a silyl-to-hydroxy conversion revealed that our fears were not groundless. Starting with the acetate **7**, and using mercury(II) acetate to re-

move the phenyl group from the silicon⁵, the product was a mixture of the primary alcohol **3**, the secondary alcohol **4**, and the diacetate **8**. The minor product **4** was a result of the

Scheme 1

very 1,3-shift about which we had been concerned. Since we had both of them, the monoacetates were easy to distinguish by the chemical shifts of the protons next to the oxygen functions, and silylation of the primary hydroxyl in the minor product **4** gave us an authentic sample of the silyl ether **6** with the two protecting groups in the wrong places.

It was easy to avoid the formation of the minor alcohol **4**, which, like the formation of the diacetate **8**, had probably been caused by the necessarily acidic reaction conditions we had used in the silyl-to-hydroxy conversion, by turning to our other one-pot method. Treatment of the silane **7** with potassium bromide in a buffered mixture of peracetic acid and acetic acid, gave the secondary alcohol **3** in good yield. To our surprise, when we tried to make the triisopropylsilyl ether of this compound using the standard recipe of

triisopropylsilyl trifluoromethanesulfonate and 2,6-lutidine, we obtained neither the secondary silyl ether **5** nor the primary **6**. Instead, we obtained the silyl ethers **9** and **10** of the two possible stereoisomers of the tetrahedral intermediate involved in the 1,3-shift. The closest parallels to this reaction of which we are aware are two very similar examples of

the silylation of the tetrahedral intermediate produced by intramolecular attack of a hindered secondary alcohol on the carbonyl group of a cyclic imide⁶. These reactions are more understandable, since the imide carbonyl may in fact have been silylated before the tetrahedral intermediate is formed. Even if it is not, the imide carbonyl group is more electrophilic than our ester carbonyl, and it is therefore easier to understand why a tetrahedral intermediate might be present in high enough concentration to be the species that is silylated. The trapping of the tetrahedral intermediate also resembles similar reactions in the O-to-C migration of acyl groups⁷, but in those reactions the oxyanion was a fully developed intermediate, the high concentration of which can explain why it was the species to be trapped. In our reaction, with lutidine as the base, it is unlikely that the oxyanion has a high concentration, and so it is even less obvious why silylation has taken place, selectively and in high yield, on neither the primary nor the secondary hydroxyls, but on the tertiary hydroxyl of the tetrahedral intermediate. What we can say is that this is not thermodynamically controlled – on standing for a few weeks, the mixture of silyl ethers **9** and **10** rearranged to give the primary silyl ether **6**.

The structures of these two compounds were most tellingly revealed by the complete absence of carbonyl stretching absorption in the IR spectra, and confirmed by a full assignment (COSY) of the ¹H NMR spectra. The assignment of stereochemistry followed from the presence in the ¹H NMR spectrum of the major isomer of a strong NOE enhancement from the axial methyl group to the axial hydrogens **11**.

Thus we had now suffered both a complete transfer of the protecting group, and a half-way transfer, but we still did not have the isomer we wanted. We avoided the problem simply by starting with the pivaloyl ester **12** in place of the acetate **3**, since pivaloyl groups are less apt to give orthoesters⁸. The silyl-to-hydroxy conversion **12** → **13** was uneventful, the silylation **13** → **14** appeared to go smoothly, the removal of the pivaloyl group gave us an alcohol, and oxidation gave us the aldehyde we wanted **2**, showing that all the structures were correct, and that we had not been led astray. The aldehyde was identical with a sample prepared by a completely different method with highly predictable stereochemistry⁹, which we hope to describe in full in another paper, when the synthesis is complete.

Scheme 4

Experimental

Light petroleum refers to the fraction boiling in the range 40–60°. In ^1H NMR spectra, coupling constants J are expressed in Hz. In ^{13}C NMR attached-proton test (APT) spectra, + denotes a signal in the same direction as the NMR solvent signal.

(2*RS*,3*RS*,4*RS*)-2,4-Dimethyl-3-dimethyl(phenyl)-silylhexyl acetate (7) : Acetic anhydride (0.11 cm³, 1.2 mmol) was added dropwise to a stirred solution of alcohol 1 (0.25 g, 0.96 mmol) and 4-dimethylaminopyridine (0.14 g, 1.15 mmol) in dry dichloromethane (10 cm³) at 0° under argon. The mixture was allowed to warm to room temperature and stirred overnight. The reaction was quenched at 0° with water (3 cm³) and the mixture extracted with ether (3×15 cm³). The organic layers were combined, washed with aqueous hydrochloric acid (3 mol dm⁻³, 15 cm³) and saturated aqueous sodium hydrogen carbonate solution (2×10 cm³), dried (MgSO_4) and concentrated under reduced pressure. The residue was chromatographed (SiO_2 , EtOAc -light petroleum, 1 : 4) to give the acetate (0.26 g, 88%) as an oil : R_f (EtOAc -light petroleum, 1 : 4) 0.56 v_{max} (film)/cm⁻¹ 1739 (C=O), 1231 (SiMe) and 1109 (SiPh); δ_{H} (250 MHz; CDCl_3) 7.57–7.51 (2H, m, Ph), 7.40–7.30 (3H, m, Ph), 3.78 (2H, d, J 7.5, CH_2OAc), 2.18–2.05 (1H, m, $\text{MeCHCH}_2\text{OAc}$), 2.03 (3H, s, OCOCH_3), 1.68 (1H, dsxtet,

J 1.8 and 7.0, EtCHMe), 1.35–1.21 (2H, m, MeCH_2), 1.20 (1H, br t, J 1.8, CHSi), 1.04 (3H, d, J 7.0, EtCHMe), 0.91 (3H, d, J 7.0 $\text{MeCHCH}_2\text{OAc}$), 0.79 (3H, t, J 7.3, CH_2Me), 0.43 (3H, s, SiMe_AMe_B) and 0.41 (3H, s, SiMe_AMe_B); δ_{C} (250 MHz; CDCl_3) 171.0+, 140.2+, 133.9–, 128.7–, 127.7–, 69.9+, 35.1–, 32.5–, 31.0–, 29.7+, 21.0–, 18.6–, 18.4–, 12.4–, –0.5– and –0.9–; m/z (EI) 291 (11%, $\text{M}^+ - \text{Me}$), 246 (55, $\text{M}^+ - \text{AcOH}$) and 135 (100, SiMe_2Ph) (Found $\text{M}^+ - \text{Me}$, 291.1771 $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}_2\text{Si} - \text{Me}$ requires M , 291.1780).

Mercuric ion-induced silyl-to-hydroxy conversion of (2*RS*,3*RS*,4*RS*)-3-dimethyl(phenyl)silyl-2,4-dimethylhexyl acetate : Mercuric acetate (0.18 g, 0.56 mmol) was added to a stirred solution of the β -silyl acetate 7 (0.14 g, 0.47 mmol) in peracetic acid (6.7 cm³ of a 32% w/w solution in acetic acid). The turbid solution was stirred at room temperature for 5 h. Ether (100 cm³) was added and the mixture washed with saturated aqueous sodium thiosulfate solution (2×10 cm³), water (10 cm³), saturated aqueous sodium hydrogen carbonate solution (2×10 cm³) and brine (10 cm³). The ether solution was dried (Na_2SO_4) and evaporated under reduced pressure. Chromatography (SiO_2 ; EtOAc -hexane, 1 : 4) gave the (2*RS*,3*RS*,4*RS*)-3-hydroxy-2,4-dimethylhexyl acetate 3 (31 mg, 35%) as an oil . R_f (EtOAc -hexane, 1 : 4) 0.22; v_{max} (CHCl_3)/cm⁻¹ 3463 (OH) and 1722 (C=O); δ_{H} (500 MHz; CDCl_3) 4.19 (1H, dd, J 10.9 and 8.1, $\text{CH}_A\text{H}_B\text{OAc}$), 3.92 (1H, dd, J 10.9 and 5.8, $\text{CH}_A\text{H}_B\text{OAc}$), 3.27 (1H, dd, J 8.8 and 2.5, CHOH), 2.06 (3H, s, OAc), 2.05–1.92 (1H, m, $\text{MeCHCH}_2\text{OAc}$), 1.76 (1H, dsxtet, J 3.1 and 7.6, EtCHMe), 1.47 (1H, br m, MeCH_AH_B), 1.13 (1H, br m, MeCH_AH_B), 0.9 (3H, t, J 7.4, MeCH_2), 0.87 (3H, d, J 6.9, EtCHMe) and 0.81 (3H, d, J 6.8, $\text{MeCHCH}_2\text{OAc}$); δ_{C} (250 MHz; CDCl_3) 171+, 74.6–, 67.5+, 37.3–, 34.5–, 25.3+, 20.9–, 15.0–, 11.0– and 9.2–; m/z (TOF) 211 (100%, $\text{M}^+ + \text{Na}$) (Found : $\text{M}^+ + \text{Na}$, 211.1300. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_3 + \text{Na}$ requires M , 211.1412); (2*RS*,3*RS*,4*RS*)-2,4-dimethyl-1-hydroxyhex-3-yl acetate 4 (8 mg, 9%) as an oil : R_f (EtOAc -hexane, 1 : 4) 0.17; v_{max} (CHCl_3)/cm⁻¹ 3462 (OH) and 1732 (C=O); δ_{H} (250 MHz; CDCl_3) 4.81 (1H, dd, J 9.8 and 2.2, CHOAc), 3.41 (1H, dd, J 11.9 and 5.4, $\text{CH}_A\text{H}_B\text{OH}$), 3.13 (1H, dd, J 11.9 and 10.0, $\text{CH}_A\text{H}_B\text{OH}$), 2.1 (3H, s, OCOCH_3), 2.09–1.80 (1H, m, CHMeCH_2OH), 1.79–1.65 (1H, m, EtCHMe), 1.55–1.38 (1H, m, MeCH_AH_B), 1.20–1.0 (1H, m, MeCH_AH_B), 0.87 (3H, t, J 7.3, MeCH_2), 0.86 (3H, d, J 6.8, CHMeCH_2OH) and 0.77 (3H, d, J 6.9, EtCHMe); δ_{C} (250 MHz; CDCl_3) 166+, 76.8+, 64.2+, 36.5–, 35.1–, 25.5+, 20.8–, 14.7–, 10.5– and 9.1–; m/z (TOF) 211 (100%, $\text{M}^+ + \text{Na}$) (Found : $\text{M}^+ + \text{Na}$, 211.1300. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_3 + \text{Na}$ requires M , 211.1310); and (2*RS*,3*RS*,4*RS*)-3-acetoxy-2,4-dimethyl-

hexyl acetate **8** (41 mg, 20%) as an oil : R_f (EtOAc-hexane, 1 : 4) 0.40; ν_{\max} (CHCl₃)/cm⁻¹ 1729 (C=O); δ_H (250 MHz; CDCl₃) 4.86 (1H, dd, J 8.4 and 3.5, CHOAc), 3.93 (1H, dd, J 11.0 and 7.5, CH_AH_BOAc), 3.83 (1H, dd, J 11.0 and 6.3, CH_AH_BOAc), 2.17 (1H, m, MeCHCH₂OAc), 2.05 (6H, s, 2×OAc), 1.67 (1H, m, EtCHMe), 1.42 (1H, m, MeCH_AH_B), 1.07 (1H, m, MeCH_AH_B), 0.91 (3H, d, J 6.8, EtCHMe), 0.88 (3H, t, J 7.2, MeCH₂) and 0.87 (3H, d, J 6.8, MeCHCH₂OAc); δ_C (250 MHz; CDCl₃) 171+, 76.6-, 66.5+, 35.9-, 33.6-, 24.6+, 20.9-, 15.0-, 11.1- and 10.6-; m/z (TOF) 253 (100%, M⁺ + Na) (Found : M⁺ + Na, 253.1410. C₁₂H₂₂O₄ + Na requires M, 253.1415).

(2RS,3RS,4RS)-2,4-Dimethyl-1-trisopropylsilyloxyhex-3-yl acetate (**6**) : 2,6-Lutidine (0.018 cm³, 0.15 mmol) was added to the hydroxy acetate **4** (10 mg, 0.05 mmol) in dry dichloromethane (1 cm³) under argon at room temperature. Triisopropylsilyl triflate (0.028 cm³, 0.10 mmol) was added and the mixture stirred for 30 min. Water (1 cm³) was added and the mixture diluted with dichloromethane (20 cm³). The aqueous layer was extracted with dichloromethane (3×10 cm³) and the combined organic fractions was washed with pH 7 buffer (2×10 cm³), dried (Na₂SO₄), filtered and evaporated. The residue was chromatographed (SiO₂, CH₂Cl₂-light petroleum, 4 : 1) to give the silyl ether **6** (13 mg, 72%) as an oil : R_f (CH₂Cl₂-light petroleum, 4 : 1) 0.62; ν_{\max} (film)/cm⁻¹ 1722 (C=O); δ_H (500 MHz; CDCl₃) 4.87 (1H, dd, J 7.4 and 4.2, CHOAc), 3.59 (1H, dd, J 9.6 and 6.0, CH_AH_BOSi), 3.42 (1H, dd, J 9.6 and 7.0, CH_AH_BOSi), 2.03 (3H, s, OAc), 1.98 (1H, m, MeCHCH₂OSi), 1.68 (1H, m, EtCHMe), 1.46 (1H, m, MeCH_AH_B), 1.30 (1H, m, MeCH_AH_B), 1.10–0.98 (21H, m, Si¹Pr₃) and 0.84 (9H, m, MeCH₂CHMe and MeCHCH₂O); m/z (EI) 301 (21%, M⁺-Ac) (Found : M⁺-Ac, 301.2204. C₁₉H₄₀O₃Si-Ac requires M, 301.2562).

(2RS,3RS,4RS)-3-Hydroxy-2,4-dimethylhexyl acetate (**3**) : Potassium bromide (46 mg, 0.39 mmol) and anhydrous sodium acetate (83 mg, 0.33 mmol) were added to a stirred solution of the acetate **7** (100 mg, 0.32 mmol) in glacial acetic acid (0.83 cm³). Peracetic acid (0.83 cm³) was then added dropwise to the mixture with ice-cooling. More sodium acetate (249 mg) and peracetic acid (2.49 cm³) were added to the mixture and the turbid solution was stirred at room temperature for 18 h and at 35° for 1 h. Ether (50 cm³) and powder aqueous sodium thiosulfate (2 g) were added and the mixture was stirred vigorously for 0.5 h, filtered through celite and evaporated under reduced pressure. The residue was taken up in ether and washed with aqueous saturated sodium hydrogen carbonate (3×10 cm³) and brine, dried (Na₂SO₄) and evaporated under reduced pressure. The residue was chromatographed (SiO₂, EtOAc-light petro-

leum, 1 : 4) to give the hydroxy acetate **3** (50 mg, 83%) identical (TLC, IR, ¹H NMR) with the sample described above; and (2RS,3RS,4RS)-2,4-dimethyl-3-dimethyl-(hydroxy)silylhexyl acetate : R_f (EtOAc-light petroleum, 1 : 4) 0.28; ν_{\max} (CHCl₃)/cm⁻¹ 3457 (OH) and 1738 (C=O); δ_H (250 MHz; CDCl₃) 4.10 (1H, dd, J 10.7 and 7.3, CH_AH_BOAc), 3.90 (1H, dd, J 10.7 and 7.1, CH_AH_BOAc), 2.10 (1H, m, MeCHCH₂OAc), 2.05 (3H, s, OAc), 1.66 (1H, dsxtet, J 2.6 and 6.9, EtCHMe), 1.44–1.20 (3H, m, MeCH₂CHMeCHSi), 1.09 (3H, d, J 7.0, MeCHCH₂OAc), 0.96 (3H, d, J 7.0, EtCHMe), 0.86 (3H, t, J 7.4, MeCH₂), 0.22 (3H, s, SiMe_AMe_B) and 0.18 (3H, s, SiMe_AMe_B); δ_C (250 MHz; CDCl₃) 171.4+, 70.2+, 35.0-, 33.4-, 30.9-, 29.6+, 21.0-, 18.8-, 17.9-, 12.4-, 22.2- and 2.0-; m/z (EI) 228 (2%, M⁺-H₂O) (Found : M⁺-H₂O, 228.1535. C₁₂H₂₆O₃Si-H₂O requires M, 228.1545).

(2SR,4RS,5RS)-4[(2RS)-2-Butyl]-2,5-dimethyl-2-trisopropylsilyloxy-1,3-dioxane (**9**) and (2RS,4RS,5RS)-4[(2RS)-2-butyl]-2,5-dimethyl-2-trisopropylsilyloxy-1,3-dioxane (**10**) : 2,6-Lutidine (0.041 cm³, 0.35 mmol) was added to a solution of the hydroxy acetate **3** (21 mg, 0.12 mmol) in dry dichloromethane (2 cm³) under argon at room temperature. Triisopropylsilyl triflate (0.062 cm³, 0.23 mmol) was added and the mixture stirred for 30 min. Water (1 cm³) was added and the mixture diluted with dichloromethane (50 cm³). The aqueous layer was extracted with dichloromethane (3×10 cm³) and the combined organic fractions was washed with pH 7 buffer (2×10 cm³), dried (Na₂SO₄), filtered and evaporated. The residue was chromatographed (SiO₂, CH₂Cl₂-light petroleum, 4 : 1) to give the *ortho*-ester **9** (19.6 mg, 52%) as an oil : R_f (CH₂Cl₂-light petroleum, 4 : 1) 0.68; ν_{\max} (film)/cm⁻¹ (no assignable peaks); δ_H (250 MHz; CDCl₃) 3.99 (1H, dd, J 11.6 and 3.6, CH_AH_BO), 3.70 (1H, dd, J 11.6 and 2.1, CH_AH_BO), 3.47 (1H, dd, J 9.9 and 2.9, OCHCHMe), 1.72 (1H, dsxtet, J 2.9 and 7.6, MeCHCH₂O), 1.56 (3H, s, SiOCMe), 1.46 (1H, m, EtCHMe), 1.23–1.14 (2H, m, MeCH₂), 1.13–1.02 (24H, m, Si¹Pr₃ and MeCHCH₂O), 0.84 (3H, t, J 7.4, MeCH₂) and 0.77 (3H, d, J 6.8, EtCHMe); δ_C (250 MHz; CDCl₃) 111.9+, 78.3-, 68.9+, 35.1-, 29.5-, 24.9+, 20.8-, 18.1-, 13.6-, 13.4-, 13.0-, 11.0- and 10.1-; m/z (EI) 329 (18%, M⁺-Me) and 301 (37, M⁺-COMe) (Found : M⁺-Me, 329.2501. C₁₉H₄₀O₃Si-Me requires M, 329.2511); and the *ortho*-ester **10** (11.3 mg, 30%) as an oil, R_f (CH₂Cl₂-light petroleum, 4 : 1) 0.52; ν_{\max} (CHCl₃)/cm⁻¹ (no assignable peaks); δ_H (250 MHz; CDCl₃) 4.34 (1H, dd, J 10.9 and 2.7, CH_AH_BO), 3.91 (1H, dd, J 10.2 and 2.3, OCH), 3.46 (1H, dd, J 10.9 and 1.5, CH_AH_BO), 1.72 (1H, m, MeCHCH₂O), 1.58 (3H, s, SiOCMe), 1.45 (1H, br m, EtCHMe), 1.20–1.14 (2H, m, MeCH₂). 1.12–

1.02 (24H, m, Si¹Pr₃ and MeCHCH₂O), 0.86 (3H, t, *J* 7.4, MeCH₂) and 0.77 (3H, d, *J* 6.8, EtCHMe); δ_c (250 MHz; CDCl₃) 109.5+, 74.1-, 66.4+, 35.2-, 29.6-, 28.0-, 25.0+, 20.8-, 18.2-, 13.7-, 13.5-, 13.3-, 11.1- and 10.5-; *m/z* (EI) 329 (58%, M⁺-Me) and 301 (50, M⁺-COMe) (Found : M⁺-Me, 329.2516. C₁₉H₄₀O₃Si-Me requires M, 329.2511).

(2RS,3RS,4RS)-3-Dimethyl(phenyl)silyl-2,4-dimethylhexyl 2,2-dimethylpropionate (**12**) : The alcohol **1** (50 mg, 0.18 mmol) was dissolved in dichloromethane (5 cm³) and cooled in an ice-bath (0°). Triethylamine (0.079 cm³, 0.56 mmol) was added, followed by pivaloyl chloride (0.028 cm³, 0.22 mmol) with constant stirring. A few crystals of 4-dimethylaminopyridine were added and the mixture was stirred at 0° for 2 h. The resulting solution was stirred at room temperature for 30 h, then poured into water (10 cm³) and extracted with ether (2×15 cm³). The extract was washed with dilute hydrochloric acid, saturated aqueous sodium hydrogen carbonate (3×10 cm³), brine (2×10 cm³), and water (2×10 cm³). The organic layer was dried (MgSO₄) and evaporated under reduced pressure. The residue was chromatographed (SiO₂, EtOAc-light petroleum, 1 : 4) to give the pivalate **12** (0.66 mg, 98%) as an oil : *R_f* (EtOAc-light petroleum, 1 : 4) 0.87; *v*_{max} (film)/cm⁻¹ 1728 (C=O), 1249 (SiMe₂) and 1106 (SiPh); δ_H (250 MHz; CDCl₃) 7.54–7.49 (2H, m, Ph), 7.36–7.31 (3H, m, Ph), 3.80 (1H, dd, *J* 7.5 and 4.2, CH_AH_BOPiv), 3.72 (1H, dd, *J* 7.5 and 4.6, CH_AH_BOPiv), 2.11 (1H, dsxtet, *J* 2.2 and 7.2, MeCHCH₂O), 1.67 (1H, dsxtet, *J* 1.8 and 6.8, EtCHMe), 1.27 (3H, s, CMe_AMe_BMe_C), 1.20 (6H, s, CMe_AMe_BMe_C), 1.19–1.16 (3H, m, MeCH₂ and CHSi), 1.03 (3H, d, *J* 7.0, EtCHMe), 0.90 (3H, d, *J* 7.0, MeCHCH₂OPiv), 0.78 (3H, t, *J* 7.4, MeCH₂), 0.41 (3H, s, SiMe_AMe_B) and 0.39 (3H, s, SiMe_AMe_B); δ_c (250 MHz; CDCl₃) 178.4+, 140.3+, 133.8-, 128.7-, 127.7-, 69.7+, 38.8+, 35.1-, 33.1-, 31.2-, 30.3+, 27.3-, 26.5-, 18.4-, 18.4-, 12.6-, -0.4- and -0.9-; *m/z* (EI) 246 (40%, M⁺-Me₃CCOOi) and 135 (100, SiMe₂Ph) (Found : M⁺-Me₃CCOOH, 246.1799. C₂₁H₃₆O₂Si-Me₃CCOOH requires M, 246.1803).

(2RS,3RS,4RS)-2,4-Dimethyl-3-hydroxyhexyl 2,2-dimethylpropionate (**13**) : Potassium bromide (26 mg, 0.22 mmol) and anhydrous sodium acetate (47 mg, 0.18 mmol) were added to a stirred solution of the pivalate **12** (57 mg, 0.18 mmol) in glacial acetic acid (0.047 cm³). Peracetic acid (0.047 cm³) was added dropwise to the mixture with ice-cooling. More sodium acetate (141 mg) and peracetic acid (1.41 cm³) were added to the mixture and the turbid solution was stirred at room temperature for 18 h and at 35° for 1 h. Ether (40 cm³) and powdered aqueous saturated sodium thiosulfate (1 g) were added and the mixture was

stirred vigorously for 0.5 h, filtered through celite and evaporated under reduced pressure. The residue was taken up in ether and washed with aqueous saturated sodium hydrogen carbonate (3×10 cm³), brine (10 cm³), the organic layer dried (Na₂SO₄) and evaporated under reduced pressure. The residue was chromatographed (SiO₂, EtOAc-light petroleum, 1 : 4) to give the hydroxy pivalate **13** (30 mg, 74%) as an oil : *R_f* (EtOAc-light petroleum, 1 : 4) 0.38; *v*_{max} (CHCl₃)/cm⁻¹ 3462 (OH) and 1732 (C=O); δ_H (250 MHz; CDCl₃) 4.22 (1H, dd, *J* 10.9 and 7.9, CH_AH_BOPiv), 3.92 (1H, dd, *J* 10.9 and 5.6, CH_AH_BOPiv), 3.27 (1H, dd, *J* 8.7 and 2.7, CHOH), 1.83–1.69 (2H, m, EtCHMe and CHMeCH₂O), 1.52–1.42 (2H, m, MeCH₂), 1.21 (9H, s, COCMe₃), 0.90 (3H, t, *J* 6.7, MeCH₂), 0.89 (3H, d, *J* 6.8, EtCHMe) and 0.82 (3H, d, *J* 6.7, MeCHCH₂O); *m/z* (TOF) 253 (M⁺ + Na) (Found : M⁺ + Na, 253.1769. C₁₃H₂₆O₃ + Na requires M, 253.1779).

(2RS,3RS,4RS)-2,4-Dimethyl-3-triisopropylsilyloxyhexyl 2,2-dimethylpropionate (**14**) : 2,6-Lutidine (0.011 cm³, 0.10 mmol) was added to the hydroxy pivalate **13** (8 mg, 0.03 mmol) in dry dichloromethane (1 cm³) under argon at room temperature. Triisopropylsilyl triflate (0.018 cm³, 0.07 mmol) was added and the mixture stirred for 30 min. Water (1 cm³) was added and the mixture diluted with dichloromethane (20 cm³). The aqueous layer was extracted with dichloromethane (3×10 cm³) and the combined organic fractions was washed with pH 7 buffer (2×10 cm³), dried (Na₂SO₄), filtered and evaporated. The residue was chromatographed (SiO₂, CH₂Cl₂-light petroleum, 1 : 1) to give the silyl ether **14** (12 mg, 92%) as an oil : *R_f* (CH₂Cl₂-light petroleum, 2 : 3) 0.48; *v*_{max} (film)/cm⁻¹ 1732 (C=O); δ_H (250 MHz; CDCl₃) 3.94 (2H, br d, *J* 6.5, CH₂OPiv), 3.86 (1H, dd, *J* 4.5 and 1.9, CHOSi), 1.98 (1H, br septet, *J* 7.4, MeCHCH₂OPiv), 1.62 (1H, br m, EtCHMe), 1.50–1.30 (2H, m, MeCH₂), 1.15 (9H, s, OCMe₃) 1.09 (21H, s, Si¹Pr₃) and 1.0–0.85 (9H, m, MeCH₂ and 2×CHMe).

(2RS,3RS,4RS)-2,4-Dimethyl-3-triisopropylsilyloxyhexanol : The ester **14** (5 mg, 0.012 mmol) in ether (0.5 cm³) was added slowly to a stirred suspension of lithium aluminium hydride (2 mg, 0.5 mmol) in ether (0.5 cm³) under argon at -40°. The suspension was stirred at this temperature for 30 min before being quenched with water and allowed to warm to room temperature. The mixture was extracted with ether and the combined ether layers dried (Na₂SO₄) and evaporated under reduced pressure. Chromatography (SiO₂, CH₂Cl₂-light petroleum, 1 : 1) gave the alcohol (**3** mg, 83%) as an oil : *R_f* (CH₂Cl₂-light petroleum, 4 : 1) 0.27; *v*_{max} (film)/cm⁻¹ 3600–3080 (OH), 1255 (SiMe₂), 1050 (SiO) and 840 (SiMe₂); δ_H (250 MHz; CDCl₃) 3.88 (1H, dd, *J* 4.3 and 2.2, CHOSi), 3.63 (1H, br

t, J 10.0, $\text{CH}_A\text{H}_B\text{O}$), 3.50 (1H, br t, J 10.5, $\text{CH}_A\text{H}_B\text{O}$), 1.88 (1H, m, MeCHCH_2OH), 1.72 (1H, m, EtCHMe), 1.59 (1H, m, MeCH_AH_B), 1.43 (1H, m, MeCH_AH_B), 1.09 (21H, s, Si^iPr_3), 0.95 (3H, d, J 6.9, MeCHCH_2O), 0.92 (3H, t, J 6.5, MeCH_2) and 0.91 (3H, d, J 7.4, EtCHMe).

(2RS, 3RS, 4RS)-2,4-Dimethyl-3-triisopropylsilyloxyhexanal (**2**): Tetrapropylammonium perruthenate (1 mg) was added to a stirred mixture of the alcohol (3 mg, 0.01 mmol), *N*-methylmorpholine *N*-oxide (3 mg, 0.03 mmol) and powder 4 Å molecular sieves (5 mg) in dichloromethane (0.02 cm^3) at room temperature under argon. After 2 h, the mixture was filtered through a short pad of silica, eluting with dichloromethane. The filtrate was evaporated to give the aldehyde **2** (2 mg, 74%) as an oil: R_f (CH_2Cl_2 -light petroleum, 4 : 1) 0.61; ν_{max} (film)/ cm^{-1} 2709 (CHO), 1726 (C=O), 1247 (Si-C) and 1104 (Si-O) and 882 (Si-C); δ_{H} (250 MHz; CDCl_3) 9.81 (1H, d, J 0.9, CHO), 4.26 (1H, dd, J 4.3 and 3.5, CHOSi), 2.48 (1H, qdd, J 7.0, 3.5 and 0.9, COCHMe), 1.65 (1H, m, EtCHMe), 1.37 (1H, m, MeCH_AH_B), 1.15 (3H, d, J 7.0, COCHMe), 1.10 (1H, m, MeCH_AH_B), 1.05 (21H, s, Si^iPr_3), 0.92 (3H, d, J 6.9, EtCHMe) and 0.90 (3H, t, J 7.4, MeCH_2), identical (TLC, IR, ^1H NMR) with the enantiomerically pure sample prepared earlier, when the following additional data were collected: δ_{C} (100 MHz; CDCl_3) 205.4, 75.0, 49.7, 41.0, 26.0, 18.3, 15.0, 12.9, 12.2 and 9.3; m/z 301 (2.6%, $\text{M}^+ + \text{H}$), 273 (33, $\text{M}-\text{C}_2\text{H}_5$), 257 (100, $\text{M}-^i\text{Pr}$), 243 (37, $\text{M}-\text{CHMeEt}$), 215 (18, $\text{M}-\text{CHMeEt}-\text{CO}$), 171 (52, $\text{M}-\text{CHMeEt}-\text{CHO}-^i\text{Pr}$), 157 (8, Si^iPr_3), 143 (26, $\text{M}-\text{Si}^i\text{Pr}_3$), 131 (8, $^i\text{Pr}_2\text{Si}=\text{OH}$) and 75 (8, $\text{Me}_2\text{Si}=\text{OH}$) (Found: $\text{M}^+ + \text{H}$, 301.2567. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{37}\text{SiO}_2$ requires $\text{M} + \text{H}$, 301.2562); $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{20} +19.9$ (c. 1.3 in CDCl_3).

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